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Executive Summary

This document, D3.1 - System Specifications, defines the analytical requirements and design methodologies for Current Limiting (CL) devices intended for DC and hybrid AC/DC microgrid infrastructures. The content is aligned with the NOVETROL project's objective of enabling safe and efficient power flow control in climate-neutral energy systems.

As included in the Description of Action, the requirements for the EMR-components are selected to comply to the different use-case scenarios and applications identified in T2.1. The specifications of the EMR components will be considered for each operating mode of the CL device (Fault current limiter - FCL, tuneable current limiter - TCL, and pre-charger - PC), in the use-cases defined by UPB and ACT. Real-device and components behaviour obtained through the other WP3 tasks will help to further refine the requirements for the different use-case scenarios modelled in T2.2.

After a brief review of the existing technologies and solutions for current limiting devices, the specifications definition starts by establishing mathematical models for the main components of the current limiter, the magnetic field generator and the EMR chips, and then combines these models to describe overall system behaviour. It also describes how magnetic flux density, inductance, and extraordinary magnetoresistance affect the resistance, efficiency, and fault current under different operating conditions.

The document introduces a multi-objective optimization framework to determine optimal design parameters for each use case. The optimization aims to minimize fault current while maximizing efficiency, subject to geometric, volumetric, and performance constraints. For example, the use case for a 48V, 20A system demonstrates the approach, achieving an efficiency of 99.5% and limiting fault current to 264A.

The five High-Level Use Cases (HLUC) described in Deliverable 2.1 are considered: photovoltaic installations, battery storage, DC-operated loads, hybrid AC/DC grids, and electric vehicle charging. The functional parameters can be classified in 30 specific scenarios grouped into three current bins ranging from below 50A to 1600A, covering power levels from small residential systems to high-power industrial applications. Each scenario was analysed to identify optimized designs, all of which achieved efficiencies above 98%. To improve economic viability, a down-selection process reduced the number of design variants from 30 to 10 while assuring compliance with performance criteria.

The document concludes that proposed system specifications can be used in the main use cases, at the same time outlining next steps, including validating optimized designs through simulation and real-world testing, further reducing design variants for cost-effectiveness, and preparing integration guidelines for DC distribution standards. Scalability for high-power applications such as industrial processes and megawatt EV charging is also identified as a future focus.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CL	Current Limiter
DC	Direct Current
EMR	Extraordinary Magnetoresistance
MMF	Magnetomotive Force
NTC	Negative Temperature Coefficient
PTC	Positive Temperature Coefficient
MOSFET	Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistor
IGBT	Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor
SCR	Silicon Controlled Rectifier
SSCB	Solid-State Circuit Breaker
HVDC	High Voltage DC
FCL	Fault Current Limiter
TCL	Tuneable Current Limiter
PC	Pre-charger
EV	Electric Vehicle
SiC, GaN	Silicon Carbide, Gallium Nitride
MR	Magnetoresistance Ratio
MOO	Multi Objective Optimization
HLUC	High Level Use Case
SSH	Safe Storage at Home
CotS	Cottage in the Sun
MCS	Megawatt Charging System
WP	Work package

1. Introduction

As the Energy Transition requires increased control over power flows and efficient energy use, especially for electrical energy, a significant challenge is represented by safety measures and the prevention of dangerous operation modes. As part of the proposed solutions, Direct Current (DC) power systems are increasingly used in renewable energy, electric vehicles, data centers, and industrial applications. Protecting these systems against overcurrent and fault conditions is critical for reliability and safety. Excessive current during faults or inrush events needs to be managed, to reduce stress on components and improve system resilience. The NOVETROL project aims at developing new Current Limiting (CL) devices, based on high-mobility materials and the extraordinary magnetoresistance (EMR) effect, as well as their integration into DC and hybrid AC/DC microgrid infrastructures. The novelty of such emerging electrical distribution technology, with supply at low and medium DC voltage, given the incipient stage of standardization, requires a large effort to derive appropriate models and related worst-case scenarios for both control and optimal operation, in a sustainable framework and from a life cycle engineering perspective.

The requirements for the current limiters can be generated in an analytical way, and later be used in different use cases, as specified in deliverable 2.1. Starting with the current limiter operation, mathematical models for the current limiter concept can be extracted, leading to the requirements for each use case. Adjusting the selection criteria, a reduced number of design variants are proposed, to ensure product viability.

2. Current limiter technologies

Current limiting technologies have been proposed and implemented in electrical distribution. This section reviews state-of-the-art technologies for managing excessive DC currents across three target ranges: **20 A**, **200 A**, and **1000 A**.

2.1 Current Limiting Principles

Current limiters operate by introducing additional impedance or controlling current flow during overcurrent conditions. Their main function of a device acting as FCL in DC power systems is to reduce the maximum current value in case of faults. This limitation can impose significant stress on the current limiter itself, therefore the practical implementations use the device for a specific duration (up to 1ms or so), until the circuit protection device can interrupt the current. As the solid-state circuit breakers have a very fast operation, they do not usually require a current limiter. However, a more affordable solution is to use hybrid circuit breakers, with longer interruption times. Figure 1 shows the basic DC circuit topology employing a hybrid circuit breaker (650 μ s operation) and the effect of the inductive current limiter.

Figure 1. Basic DC circuit configuration

It can be seen from the simulation results that the current value can reach 6.2kA before the circuit breaker can interrupt the circuit, if no current limiting device is used. If a 130 μ H inductor is used, the current rises with a lower slope and the maximum current is only 2.5 kA, which is more easily managed by the circuit breaker.

If the device is operated as pre-charger, its main function is also to limit the current in the system during the charging of the DC link capacitance of a converter that is connected to an operating DC grid. This limited current must be within the operating range of the system; therefore, it will not overstress the pre-charging device. It should be mentioned that the implementation of this function may pose more challenges for the EMR material capabilities, but this objective will be addressed during the execution of WP3.

If the device must be operated as TCL, the concept is modified such that the value of the limited current can be adjusted through a control input. For a targeted value of the limited current, the operation principle is like that of FCL, therefore, we will consider the current and voltage limits. The exact concept of the TCL will be discussed in future deliverables in WP3.

Two main categories of current limiter technologies exist:

- **Passive Limiters:** This technology uses inductive or resistive/thermistor elements (e.g., NTC/PTC) to limit current during startup or fault conditions.
- **Active Limiters:** This technology employs semiconductor devices (MOSFETs, IGBTs, SCRs) with control circuits to dynamically regulate current.

The key performance metrics for a FCL device are:

- **Response time** (critical for DC faults due to lack of zero-crossing).
- **Voltage drop** during normal operation.
- **Thermal management** under sustained overload.
- **Reset capability** (self-recoverable vs. sacrificial devices).

2.2 Technologies for 20 A Range

Passive Thermistor-Based Limiters

NTC Thermistors: This solution uses the changes of the material resistance when the temperature of the device increases at high currents. High initial resistance limits inrush current, while the resistance decreases as temperature rises. Common usage is for power supplies and battery chargers.

- Example: Ametherm SL22 series rated 20 A continuous current. [1] [2]
- Advantages: Low cost, simple design.
- Limitations: Slow recovery, temperature-dependent performance.

Active MOSFET-Based Limiters

Use MOSFETs in linear mode with current sensing and control devices.

- Example: MAX17523 electronic circuit protector for adjustable current limiting [3].
- Advantages: Fast response, precise control.
- Limitations: Requires heat sinking and SOA management.

2.3 Technologies for 200 A Range

Solid-State Limiters

This solution uses a hybrid designs combining MOSFET arrays and inductive elements for fault current suppression.

- Example: ABB's solid-state fault current limiters for DC distribution systems [4]

- Advantages: Ultrafast operation (<1 ms), coordination with DC circuit breakers.

High-Power Thermistor Solutions

This solution uses high current (industrial grade) NTC limiters (e.g., Ametherm MegaSurge series) rated up to 80 A continuous. The main applications are motor drives and UPS systems. [2]. For 200 A, typically bypass contactors are used to reduce losses after startup.

Active Semiconductor Limiters

This solution uses multi-MOSFET or IGBT stacks with microcontroller-based control and implements special techniques such **foldback limiting** or **hiccup mode** to reduce thermal stress.[5]

2.4 Technologies for 1000 A Range

These technologies are less mature, and the results are generated mainly by research projects.

Solid-State Circuit Breakers (SSCB) with Current Limiting

This solution proposes advanced SSCBs integrating latching current limiter functionality.

- Example: High-speed SSCB with clearing time ~200 ns and integrated limiter for DC grids. [6]
- Applications: HVDC systems, large battery.

Fault Current Limiters (FCLs)

Superconducting FCLs: This implementation uses superconducting materials to introduce high impedance during fault without affecting normal operation, when the impedance is negligible. Suitable for very high currents in utility-scale DC systems [7].

Self-powered solid-state FCLs: These devices are solid-state current limiters which draw energy from fault current to activate the limiting function, eliminating the external supply, thus reducing complexity [8].

Hybrid Solutions

As in the 200A range, this solution combines inductive elements, resistors, and semiconductor switches for staged limiting.

- Example: Adaptive multi-stage DC current limiter with bidirectional capability [9].

Other research topics

- Wide Bandgap Devices (SiC, GaN) for higher efficiency and faster response in SSCBs [10].
- Integration with DC protection schemes (multifunction devices) for renewable and EV infrastructure.
- Adaptive multi-stage limiters for dynamic fault management.

Table 1. Current limiting technologies comparison

Technology	Current Range	Response Time	Losses	Cost	Applications
NTC/PTC Thermistors	Up to 50 A	ms	Low	Low	Power supplies
MOSFET Limiters	20–200 A	μs	Medium	Medium	EV, battery systems
Solid-State FCL	200–1000 A	<1 ms	Low	High	HVDC, microgrids
Superconducting FCL	>1000 A	ms	Very Low	Very High	Utility-scale

3. Current Limiter Modelling and Design

This chapter focuses on the extraction of the mathematical equations that describe the current limiter with the goal to utilise these results to generate optimal design parameters for the current limiter. Given the current limiter is comprised of different components, each one will be analysed, and all relevant results will be combined to generate the overall model.

2.1 Magnetic Field Generator model

This subsection will generate equations that describe the magnetic flux density in the air gap and its dependence to the excitation current of the coils. Furthermore, the result will be used to generate the coil inductance equation, while finally other parameter equations such as the fringe factor will be extracted for future higher fidelity modelling.

To extract the equation describing the dependence of the flux density to the magnetising current, the coil will be analysed utilising its equivalent magnetic circuit. The total reluctance of the inductor is given by the sum of the reluctance of the core and the air gap, as per the following:

$$\mathcal{R}_{total} = \mathcal{R}_{core} + \mathcal{R}_{gap} = \frac{l_{core}}{\mu_r \mu_0 A_{core}} + \frac{l_{gap}}{\mu_0 A_{gap}} \quad (1)$$

Where l_{core} is the total core length, l_{gap} is the total airgap length, μ_r is the relative permeability of the core, μ_0 is the permeability of air, A_{core} is the cross section area of the core and A_{gap} is the effective cross section area of the air gap. Given that the relative permeability of core materials is significantly higher than 1, the total reluctance is dictated by the air gap reluctance, hence:

$$\mathcal{R}_{total} = \mathcal{R}_{gap} = \frac{l_{gap}}{\mu_0 A_{gap}} \quad (2)$$

The cross-section area of the air gap is always larger than the core cross section area due to the fringe effect, and correlated to the core cross section area according to the following:

$$A_{gap} = FF A_{core} \quad (3)$$

Where FF is the fringe factor, given by:

$$FF = 1 + \frac{l_{gap}}{\sqrt{A_{core}}} \ln \left(\frac{2L_{window}}{l_{gap}} \right) \quad (4)$$

Where L_{window} is the length of the window of the inductor.

The last component needed to calculate the flux in the magnetic circuit and by extension the flux density is the excitation of the circuit. The magnetomotive force, MMF, is given by:

$$MMF = NI \quad (5)$$

Where, N is the number of coil turns and I is the excitation current. The flux is therefore given by:

$$\Phi_{gap} = \frac{MMF}{\mathcal{R}_{total}} = \frac{NI}{\frac{l_{gap}}{\mu_0 A_{gap}}} = \frac{NI\mu_0 A_{gap}}{l_{gap}} \quad (6)$$

Dividing the calculated flux by the cross-section area of the air gap the flux density is given by:

$$B_{gap} = \frac{\Phi_{gap}}{A_{gap}} = \frac{NI\mu_0}{l_{gap}} = \frac{N\mu_0}{l_{gap}} I \quad (7)$$

This is the first characteristic equation of the current limiter, since it shows the relation of flux density and system current.

Before concluding this section, using Faraday's law, the inductance of the coil will be calculated:

$$V_{ind} = N \frac{d\Phi_{gap}}{dt} = \frac{N^2 \mu_0 A_{gap}}{l_{gap}} \frac{dI}{dt} \quad (8)$$

And therefore:

$$L_{ind} = \frac{N^2 \mu_0 A_{gap}}{l_{gap}} \quad (9)$$

2.2 EMR Element Model

The EMR chip is based on the extraordinary magnetoresistance effect, where high mobility materials, under application of a magnetic field change their effective resistivity, due to the deflection of their ballistic transport path. This variation in resistivity is described by:

$$\rho_{eff} = \rho_0 \left(1 + \frac{\mu_{mat}^2 B^2}{1 + \frac{\mu_{mat} B t_{EMR}}{l_{EMR}}} \right) \quad (10)$$

Where ρ_0 is the resistivity of the material under no magnetic field, μ_{mat} is the carrier mobility of the material, B is the magnetic flux density component flowing perpendicular to the conduction path of the material, t_{EMR} is the thickness of the EMR chip and l_{EMR} is the length of the chip.

Utilising the above equation for the resistivity alongside the equation for the resistance of a material the following can be extracted:

$$R_{EMR} = \frac{\rho_0 t_{EMR}}{S_{EMR}} \left(1 + \frac{\mu_{mat}^2 B^2}{1 + \frac{\mu_{mat} B t_{EMR}}{l_{EMR}}} \right) \quad (11)$$

Where S_{EMR} is the cross-section area of the conduction path in the ENR chip. For some example values for the physical parameters of the chip, the resistance dependence on the flux density is plotted in Figure 2. Expanding further on equation [11], the total resistance

variation under the effect of a magnetic field is dictated by the ratio of chip thickness to chip length, the physical interpretation of which is provided in [11]. To further understand this dependence, the quantity magnetoresistance ratio will be defined as:

$$MR = \frac{R_{EMR} - R_0}{R_0} \quad (12)$$

Where R_0 is the resistance of the chip at zero field and is equal to $\frac{\rho_0 t_{EMR}}{S_{EMR}}$. Replacing (11) in (12),

$$MR = \frac{\mu_{mat}^2 B^2}{1 + \frac{\mu_{mat} B t_{EMR}}{l_{EMR}}} \quad (13)$$

Defining the ratio,

$$r_{lt} = \frac{l_{EMR}}{t_{EMR}} \quad (14)$$

Equation (13) can be rewritten as

$$MR = \frac{\mu_{mat}^2 B^2}{1 + \frac{\mu_{mat} B}{r_{lt}}} \quad (15)$$

Expression (15) showcases that the highest possible change in resistance for a certain field applied to the device can be achieved only when the length of the chip is significantly larger than the thickness of the chip, with the maximum possible MR ratio being $\mu_{mat}^2 B^2$. Figure 33 shows the magnetoresistance ratio (MR) dependence on the geometrical parameters of the chip (r_{lt}) at 1T magnetic flux density applied perpendicular to the conduction path and for a material with a majority carrier mobility of $7m^2/Vs$.

Figure 2. EMR Chip Resistance (R_{EMR}) for (B) perpendicular to the conduction path.

Figure 3. Magnetoresistance ratio (MR) dependence on the geometrical parameters

2.3 Current Limiter Device Model

Combining the equations presented in sections 2.1 and 2.2 the mathematical model of the current limiter can be extracted. Specifically, the total resistance of the limiter can be expressed in relation to the current flowing through it, as per the following equation:

$$R_{EMR} = \frac{\rho_0 t_{EMR}}{S_{EMR}} \left(1 + \frac{\mu_{mat}^2 \left(\frac{N \mu_0 I}{l_{gap}} \right)^2}{1 + \frac{\mu_{mat} N \mu_0 I t_{EMR}}{L_{EMR}}} \right) = \frac{\rho_0 t_{EMR}}{S_{EMR}} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{\mu_{mat}^2 N^2 \mu_0^2 I^2}{l_{gap}^2}}{1 + \frac{\mu_{mat} N \mu_0 I t_{EMR}}{l_{gap} L_{EMR}}} \right) \quad (16)$$

The presented equation provides a detailed representation of the resistance of the collective EMR and field generator components and can be used to further extract valuable system metrics. Specifically, for a certain nominal operating current of the system and load rated power at the aforementioned nominal current, the efficiency of the current limiter can be expressed as

$$\eta_{sys} = \frac{V_{nom} I_{nom}}{V_{nom} I_{nom} + \frac{\rho_0 t_{EMR}}{S_{EMR}} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{\mu_{mat}^2 N^2 \mu_0^2 I_{nom}^2}{l_{gap}^2}}{1 + \frac{\mu_{mat} N \mu_0 I_{nom} t_{EMR}}{l_{gap} L_{EMR}}} \right) I_{nom}^2} \quad (17)$$

Finally, for a specified nominal operating voltage the limiting current can be calculated during a fault condition, assuming that the fault is a perfect short. In this case when steady state is achieved the total system voltage will appear on the EMR chip of the current limiter and therefore the fault current will be given as a solution of the following equation:

$$\frac{\rho_0 t_{EMR}}{S_{EMR}} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{\mu_{mat}^2 N^2 \mu_0^2 I_{fault}^2}{l_{gap}^2}}{1 + \frac{\mu_{mat} N \mu_0 I_{fault} t_{EMR}}{l_{gap} L_{EMR}}} \right) I_{fault} = V_{nom} \quad (18)$$

The above equation is a third order polynomial equation and therefore will have three solutions. For certain values of the component parameters the solution is given by

$$I_{fault} = \frac{\sqrt[3]{\sqrt{(-27a^2d + 9abc - 2b^3)^2 + 4(3ac - b^2)^3} + (-27a^2d + 9abc - 2b^3)}}{3\sqrt[3]{2}a} - \frac{b}{3a}$$

Where,

$$a = \frac{\mu_{mat}^2 N^2 \mu_0^2}{l_{gap}^2} \quad (20)$$

$$b = \frac{\mu_{mat} N \mu_0 t_{EMR}}{l_{gap} L_{EMR}} \quad (21)$$

$$c = 1 - \frac{\mu_{mat} N \mu_0 S_{EMR} V_{nom}}{l_{gap} L_{EMR} \rho_0} \quad (22)$$

$$d = - \frac{S_{EMR} V_{nom}}{t_{EMR} \rho_0} \quad (23)$$

Even though the presented equation is relatively difficult to manipulate, it will be used as the basis for the optimisation efforts presented in the following chapter.

4. Optimal Design Definition via Multi-Objective Optimisation

Given the plethora of design variables to be specified for the current limiter, it was decided to utilise multi objective optimisation to select the best set of variables for each current limiter design.

3.1 An Introduction to Multi-Objective Optimisation

Multi-objective optimisation, is a branch of mathematical optimisation that deals with problems involving more than one objective function to be optimised simultaneously, taking into consideration different constraints- linear and non-linear, for the optimisation variables. Unlike single-objective optimisation, where the goal is to find one optimal solution, multi-objective optimisation provides a set of Pareto optimal solutions. Those solutions, which are defined as the set of solutions where no objective can be improved without worsening at least one other objective, will be used to define the design parameters of the current limiter.

3.2 Objective Function Selection

A relative obvious objective function for the system is to minimise the absolute value of the current during a fault event. Therefore, equation (25) is selected as one of the objective functions of the optimisation problem.

Given the increasing focus in component efficiency, a decision was made to consider the efficiency as the second objective function. Give that the optimisation tries to minimise the objective functions, the following function will be defined to be minimised:

$$f_2 = 1 - \eta_{sys} \quad (24)$$

Therefore, the optimisation problem is defined as:

$$\min_{x \in X} \{I_{fault}, 1 - \eta_{sys}\} \quad (25)$$

Where x is the vector of design variables t_{EMR} , l_{EMR} , w_{EMR} , A_{gap} , l_{gap} and N , and X is the allowable set of vectors the design variable vector can take, defined by upper and lower limits for each variable. It should be noted that the design space was selected to include the width of the chip instead of the cross-section area, with the cross-sectional area given by

$$S_{EMR} = l_{EMR}w_{EMR} \quad (26)$$

The reason for this choice will become more apparent when considering the geometrical constraints of the design problem.

3.3 Non-Linear Constraints

Following the definition of the objective functions a set of non-linear constraints can be enforced in the problem to achieve different specification in the system, in this problem definition, three non-linear constraints were identified. Specifically, give the EMR chip need to fit perpendicularly in the air gap, it's length should always be less than the length of the

core. Assuming a core with a square cross-sectional area and ignoring the fringe effect, the first nonlinear constraint was:

$$l_{EMR} < \sqrt{A_{EMR}} \quad (27)$$

The second constraint has to do with the total volume of the current limiter. To ensure the product is competitive it needs to offer advantages when compared to already established solutions. One application case that was examined was the replacement of time buying inductors in hybrid circuit breakers with the EMR current limiter under investigation. The comparison of interest in this case is the total volume of the system and given the correlation of the size of the inductor with its total inductance at a nominal current, it was decided that the other nonlinear constraint would ensure that the inductance of the current limiter will be lower than the inductance of a time buying inductor for an equivalent application. Therefore:

$$\frac{N^2 \mu_0 A_{gap}}{l_{gap}} < L_{ind} \quad (28)$$

The final non-linear constraint sets a limit to the maximum allowable fault current the optimiser will provide as a viable solution. As an initial set-point the limit was selected to be:

$$I_{fault} < 100I_{nom} \quad (29)$$

3.4 Linear Constraints

Linear constraints are like the nonlinear constraints, where the design parameters are constrained via a system of linear equations. For the optimisation of the current limiter one linear constraint was identified. Specifically, as already mentioned the chip needs to be placed perpendicularly in the airgap and therefore the width of the chip needs to be less than the length of the airgap. Therefore, the linear constraint is:

$$w_{EMR} < l_{gap} \quad (30)$$

3.5 Example Case

To showcase the results of the optimisation problem that was described in the previous section, an optimal current limiter was designed for a selected use case. The optimization algorithms were implemented in MATLAB and Simulink. Specifically, for the optimisation the drafted script used the *gamultiobj* function from the global optimisation toolbox, which used as inputs three user defined functions: objective functions (*obj_fun.m*), non-linear constraints (*nonlin_con.m*) and linear constraints (*lin_con.m*). Moreover, for the validation of the optimisation, simulation models capturing the component physics (magnetic field generator, with the dependence of the magnetic flux on the operating current, and the EMR device, with the dependence of the resistance on the magnetic flux value) were created in Simulink, using the Simscape library.

Specifically, a current limiter was designed for to be integrated in a system with nominal voltage of 48V, maximum voltage of 52V and a maximum nominal current of 20A. Using those parameters, as well as selecting a maximum inductance of 100μH, the following pareto front of Figure 4 was extracted.

Figure 4. Pareto Front for the described optimisation problem

To ensure maximum efficiency without a significant fault current the solution selected provides an efficiency of 99.5% and a fault current of 264A. The designed parameters for this solution were:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N &= 49 \\
 l_{gap} &= 0.011m \\
 A_{gap} &= 2.51 \cdot 10^{-4}m^2 \\
 w_{EMR} &= 0.002m \\
 l_{EMR} &= 0.0155m \\
 t_{EMR} &= 0.0065m
 \end{aligned}$$

Utilising these values, a simulation can be set-up to validate the expected results, i.e., the value of the fault current and the system efficiency. The model was set-up in Simscape to ensure a combined simulation of the electrical and magnetic domain. The load is continuously supplied the peak nominal current of 20A and at 1s a perfect short circuit fault is injected. The current limiter current profile is presented in Figure5, showing the current profile through the current limiter with the effective limitation of the fault current to the designed value, after forcing a short circuit fault at 1s. Finally, the efficiency during the nominal operating condition was measured to be 99.47%.

Figure 5. Current profile through the current limiter

5. NOVETROL Uses Cases Specifications

The High-Level Use Cases (HLUC) considered in NOVETROL are described in Deliverable “D2.1 – NOVETROL Use Cases and Scenarios”. Here we are reviewing the main areas where the energy transition can be enabled by the application of DC power distribution. There are 5 HLUCs that cover fast expanding technologies for generation, storage, and common loads:

Photovoltaic installations.

These applications are covered by the High-Level Use Case 1 (HLUC1) “Cottage in the Sun - CotS”, which include small houses, for powers up to 3.5kW, up to small commercial building or group of houses, for powers up to 18kW. For NOVETROL the cases of 10A and 50A were considered, with 2 level of possible voltages, 48V for small systems, and 350V for full house or building DC distribution.

Battery storage.

This application is described by the HLUC2 “Safe Storage at Home - SSH”. However, besides the residential house application of 48V for new systems and 220V for systems that use the existing cabling, higher power applications, using 350V, were considered, for larger buildings. The main characteristic of this use case is the higher currents (100A and 200A) which can be encountered for battery discharge.

DC operated loads.

These use cases do not consider the DC power generation, but focus on the protection of the DC assets, in a DC power distribution system. The relevant voltage and power levels are specified in the HLUC3 “Safe DC at Home” (for powers up to 11kW and voltages up to 350V) and HLUC4 “Emerging DC at Work” (with high power capabilities, 1500V and up to 1-2MW power).

Hybrid AC/DC grids.

Similarly, the DC assets are considered in cases when the power distribution combines AC and DC sub-grids in the same system (usually behind the meter), in which the DC sub-grids have a bidirectional interface and integrate local generation and storage for power flow and energy optimization. These cases are also covered by HLUC3 and HLUC4.

EV charging and V2X.

The DC applications involving electric vehicles have special consideration because of the variety of voltage levels implemented (300V, 400V and 800V), as well as relatively high-power levels that are needed (up to 350kW for ultra-fast EV charging) in an automotive environment. The latest power levels implemented for heavy duty vehicles (1MW and more in the Megawatt Charging System MCS) need special consideration and are not covered in NOVETROL. HLUC5 “DC in Motion” is specifying the voltage and power levels that NOVETROL is studying.

The parameters of the high-level use cases presented in deliverable D2.1 can be classified in 30 combinations of voltage and current levels, as presented in Table 2. If we consider the current ranges that NOVETROL is targeting, we can cluster the cases within the 3 categories:

- a) Bin1: Current below 50A; power up to 40kW (Table 2a)
- b) Bin2: Current 50A - 100A; power 22kW - 120kW (Table 2b)
- c) Bin3: Current 200A - 1000A; power 150kW - 570kW (Table 2c)

Table 2a. Bin1: 20A and 40kW

Case	Current [A]	Voltage [V]	Power [W]	HLUC
20	1	48	48	Safe DC Home
21	4	48	192	Safe DC Home
1	10	48	480	CotS
3	10	350	3500	CotS
22	10	220	2200	Safe DC Home
23	16	220	3520	Safe DC Home
24	16	350	5600	Safe DC Home
25	32	350	11200	Safe DC Home
2	50	48	2400	CotS
4	50	350	17500	CotS
11	50	300	15000	DC in Motion
14	50	400	20000	DC in Motion
17	50	800	40000	DC in Motion

Table 2b. Bin 2: 20A to 200A and 22kW to 120kW

Case	Current [A]	Voltage [V]	Power [W]	HLUC
5	100	48	4800	SSH
7	100	220	22000	SSH
9	100	350	35000	SSH
26	125	350	43750	Safe DC Work
27	125	650	81250	Safe DC Work
12	150	300	45000	DC in Motion
15	150	400	60000	DC in Motion
18	150	800	120000	DC in Motion
6	200	48	9600	SSH
8	200	220	44000	SSH
10	200	350	70000	SSH

Table 2c. Bin 3: 100A to 1000A and 150kW to 570kW

Case	Current [A]	Voltage [V]	Power [W]	HLUC
28	380	650	247000	Safe DC Work
29	380	1500	570000	Safe DC Work
19	440	800	352000	DC in Motion
13	500	300	150000	DC in Motion
16	500	400	200000	DC in Motion

It should be mentioned that use case 30 (1600A and 1500V) covers special applications, such as energy intensive industries (glass and steel furnaces) and will require dedicated design.

Case	Current [A]	Voltage [V]	Power [W]	HLUC
30	1600	1500	2,400,000	Safe DC Work

6. Use Case Optimisation and Down-selection

The specifications in table 2 (a, b, c) were used to identify an optimized design for each use case, which will minimize the value of the current during limitation operation, while minimizing the losses introduced by the current limiter in the circuit, thus maximizing the efficiency. The mathematical methods used to implement the optimization are described in [11].

Table 3 (a, b, and c) is showing the optimization results for the 30 use cases. For Use Case 20, (48V, 1A), the optimization was not achieved with the proposed methodology (the mathematical iterations did not converge).

Use Case Down Selection

While the individual optimization of use cases validates the feasibility of the current limiting concept for each case, a more economically viable solution can be achieved if the number of design variants is reduced. For this purpose, each set of design parameters was used to calculate the cross-operation values of limited current and the efficiency for all the use cases in the same Bin. The results are presented in Table 4 (a, b, and c).

Table 3a. Optimized design and operation parameters for Bin 1

Use Case	Current [A]	Voltage [V]	Fault Current [A]	Efficiency	Number of Turns	Airgap Length [m]	Core Cross Section [m ²]	EMR Chip Thickness [m]	EMR Chip Length [m]	EMR Chip Width [m]
20	1	48	27.2	99.83	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
21	4	48	84.5	99.85	24	0.0012	0.00015	0.0027	0.0084	0.001
1	10	48	146.5	99.78	27	0.0029	0.00026	0.0018	0.0095	0.0012
3	10	350	333.4	99.19	80	0.0131	0.00017	0.0079	0.0012	0.001
22	10	220	159.3	99.08	25	0.0011	0.00014	0.0029	0.0075	0.001
23	16	220	229.3	99.27	48	0.004	0.00013	0.0023	0.0056	0.001
24	16	350	256.9	99.18	21	0.0014	0.00026	0.0039	0.0122	0.001
25	32	350	426.7	98.96	32	0.0051	0.00026	0.0043	0.0084	0.0012
2	50	48	429.8	99.39	36	0.0172	0.00074	0.0018	0.0133	0.0017
4	50	350	696.6	99.69	50	0.016	0.00044	0.0024	0.0155	0.0013
11	50	300	554.9	99.21	101	0.034	0.00026	0.0021	0.0058	0.0011
14	50	400	544.8	98.6	48	0.0124	0.00026	0.0076	0.0162	0.001
17	50	800	673.2	98.75	58	0.0108	0.00016	0.0022	0.0094	0.0011

Table 3b. Optimized design and operation parameters for Bin 2

Case	Current [A]	Voltage [V]	Fault Current [A]	Efficiency	Nr. of Turns	Airgap Length [m]	Core Cross Section [m ²]	EMR Chip Thickness [m]	EMR Chip Length [m]	EMR Chip Width [m]
5	100	48	813.5	99.44	24	0.0212	0.00094	0.0021	0.0299	0.0024
7	100	220	911.1	99.28	40	0.0324	0.0014	0.0063	0.0286	0.0013
9	100	350	953.8	99.26	20	0.0147	0.0015	0.0071	0.0324	0.0011
26	125	350	1197	99.37	31	0.0234	0.00052	0.0012	0.0118	0.0013
27	125	650	1157.6	98.54	50	0.0278	0.00074	0.0023	0.0169	0.0011
12	150	300	1098.6	98.09	36	0.0357	0.0017	0.0028	0.0078	0.0013
15	150	400	1211.3	98.82	14	0.015	0.00096	0.0043	0.0169	0.001
18	150	800	1429.7	98.66	8	0.0049	0.0012	0.0021	0.0282	0.0011
6	200	48	1464.4	99.2	21	0.0315	0.0054	0.0034	0.05	0.0046
8	200	220	1521.0	99.27	5	0.0082	0.0042	0.0031	0.0403	0.0011
10	200	350	1567.6	99.07	24	0.0303	0.0030	0.0028	0.027	0.0012

Table 3c. Optimized design and functional parameters for Bin 3

Case	Current [A]	Voltage [V]	Fault Current [A]	Efficiency	Number of Turns	Airgap Length [m]	Core Cross Section [m ²]	EMR Chip Thickness [m]	EMR Chip Length [m]	EMR Chip Width [m]
28	380	650	2789.0	98.68	14	0.0321	0.0031	0.0049	0.0356	0.0012
29	380	1500	3226.5	98.21	19	0.0375	0.0087	0.0016	0.0058	0.0011
19	440	800	3029.6	98.24	13	0.0352	0.0034	0.0078	0.0399	0.0011
13	500	300	3043.2	98.69	10	0.0393	0.0035	0.0034	0.0367	0.0012
16	500	400	3308.9	98.92	12	0.0423	0.0049	0.0022	0.0351	0.0011
30	1600	1500	9731.2	98.38	3	0.0326	0.0026	0.0025	0.0223	0.0011

Table 4a. Limited current and efficiency for Bin 1

Use case variants →	20 [A]	21 [A]	1 [A]	3 [A]	22 [A]	23 [A]	24 [A]	25 [A]	2 [A]	4 [A]	11 [A]	14 [A]	17 [A]
Selected design variants ↓													
21	84.82	84.82	84.82	239.42	174.55	174.55	239.42	239.42	84.82	239.42	205.34	273.47	544.51
1	148.33	148.33	148.33	365.35	294.53	294.53	365.35	365.35	148.33	365.35	340.03	388.89	693.52
3	93.23	93.23	93.23	325.40	247.74	247.74	325.40	325.40	93.23	325.40	297.53	351.38	518.65
22	78.06	78.06	78.06	235.61	162.07	162.07	235.61	235.61	78.06	235.61	202.06	269.11	535.80
23	108.48	108.48	108.48	280.58	224.11	224.11	280.58	280.58	108.48	280.58	260.37	299.38	533.08
24	98.94	98.94	98.94	253.33	202.70	202.70	253.33	253.33	98.94	253.33	235.21	273.91	545.68
25	162.63	162.63	162.63	423.41	337.87	337.87	423.41	423.41	162.63	423.41	392.79	451.89	634.44
2	429.54	429.54	429.54	998.53	815.48	815.48	998.53	998.53	429.54	998.53	933.25	1059.08	1444.04
4	295.91	295.91	295.91	697.66	567.91	567.91	697.66	697.66	295.91	697.66	651.35	740.64	1014.40
11	243.98	243.98	243.98	611.67	491.75	491.75	611.67	611.67	243.98	611.67	568.79	651.54	906.53
14	194.64	194.64	194.64	499.47	399.75	399.75	499.47	499.47	194.64	499.47	463.80	532.65	745.12
17	188.22	188.22	188.22	462.56	373.16	373.16	462.56	462.56	188.22	462.56	430.60	492.26	682.19

Efficiency

Use case variants→	20	21	1	3	22	23	24	25	2	4	11	14	17
Selected design variants ↓													
20	99.92%	98.30%	87.78%	98.32%	97.33%	92.87%	95.52%	87.67%	6.90%	80.69%	77.48%	83.11%	91.55%
21	99.97%	99.83%	99.11%	99.88%	99.81%	99.46%	99.66%	98.39%	68.28%	95.65%	94.92%	96.19%	98.10%
1	99.99%	99.93%	99.77%	99.97%	99.95%	99.88%	99.92%	99.64%	92.30%	98.94%	98.77%	99.08%	99.54%
3	99.38%	97.48%	93.44%	99.10%	98.57%	97.61%	98.50%	96.64%	57.23%	94.13%	93.16%	94.87%	97.43%
22	99.96%	99.79%	98.83%	99.84%	99.74%	99.30%	99.56%	97.98%	61.28%	94.69%	93.80%	95.35%	97.68%
23	99.96%	99.82%	99.32%	99.91%	99.85%	99.64%	99.77%	99.03%	81.19%	97.42%	96.99%	97.74%	98.87%
24	99.97%	99.85%	99.34%	99.91%	99.86%	99.62%	99.76%	98.88%	77.68%	96.94%	96.43%	97.32%	98.66%
25	99.96%	99.83%	99.51%	99.93%	99.89%	99.79%	99.87%	99.54%	91.70%	98.86%	98.67%	99.00%	99.50%
2	99.99%	99.97%	99.92%	99.99%	99.98%	99.97%	99.98%	99.96%	99.35%	99.91%	99.90%	99.92%	99.96%
4	99.99%	99.95%	99.88%	99.98%	99.97%	99.95%	99.97%	99.92%	98.57%	99.80%	99.77%	99.83%	99.91%
11	99.97%	99.88%	99.67%	99.96%	99.93%	99.88%	99.92%	99.79%	96.67%	99.54%	99.47%	99.60%	99.80%
14	99.96%	99.82%	99.52%	99.93%	99.89%	99.81%	99.88%	99.66%	94.26%	99.21%	99.08%	99.31%	99.66%
17	99.98%	99.92%	99.76%	99.97%	99.95%	99.90%	99.94%	99.76%	95.42%	99.37%	99.27%	99.45%	99.73%

Table 4b. Limited current and efficiency for Bin 2

Use case variants→	5 [A]	7 [A]	9 [A]	26 [A]	27 [A]	12 [A]	15 [A]	18 [A]	6 [A]	8 [A]	10 [A]
Selected design variants ↓											
5	827.89	1508.44	1822.99	1822.99	2359.38	1711.25	1926.26	2576.28	827.89	1508.44	1822.99
7	471.99	909.65	1117.39	1117.39	1476.73	1043.29	1186.13	1623.40	471.99	909.65	1117.39
9	416.34	801.22	983.67	983.67	1299.07	918.61	1044.02	1427.76	416.34	801.22	983.67
26	540.96	995.91	1207.04	1207.04	1567.96	1131.99	1276.45	1714.17	540.96	995.91	1207.04
27	393.03	737.45	899.23	899.23	1177.59	841.62	952.61	1290.83	393.03	737.45	899.23
12	476.79	949.95	1176.49	1176.49	1569.93	1095.59	1251.63	1730.91	476.79	949.95	1176.49
15	479.63	927.29	1138.58	1138.58	1503.21	1063.27	1208.40	1651.83	479.63	927.29	1138.58
18	482.85	875.64	1056.12	1056.12	1362.92	992.06	1115.27	1486.71	482.85	875.64	1056.12
6	1484.55	2707.12	3272.81	3272.81	4238.06	3071.81	3458.59	4628.53	1484.55	2707.12	3272.81
8	880.24	1577.69	1892.40	1892.40	2421.87	1781.02	1994.98	2633.96	880.24	1577.69	1892.40
10	713.44	1302.72	1573.16	1573.16	2032.73	1477.18	1661.77	2218.15	713.44	1302.72	1573.16

Efficiency

Use case variants →	5	7	9	26	27	12	15	18	6	8	10
Selected design variants ↓											
5	99.47%	99.88%	99.93%	99.89%	99.94%	99.80%	99.85%	99.93%	97.54%	99.46%	99.66%
7	96.90%	99.32%	99.57%	99.34%	99.65%	98.87%	99.16%	99.58%	86.69%	97.10%	98.17%
9	96.01%	99.13%	99.45%	99.14%	99.54%	98.52%	98.89%	99.44%	82.24%	96.12%	97.56%
26	98.38%	99.65%	99.78%	99.64%	99.81%	99.37%	99.53%	99.76%	92.10%	98.28%	98.92%
27	96.45%	99.23%	99.51%	99.19%	99.56%	98.54%	98.90%	99.45%	81.45%	95.95%	97.46%
12	95.87%	99.10%	99.43%	99.17%	99.55%	98.63%	98.98%	99.49%	84.87%	96.70%	97.93%
15	96.29%	99.19%	99.49%	99.25%	99.60%	98.77%	99.08%	99.54%	86.16%	96.98%	98.10%
18	98.19%	99.60%	99.75%	99.58%	99.78%	99.24%	99.43%	99.72%	90.13%	97.85%	98.65%
6	99.82%	99.96%	99.97%	99.96%	99.98%	99.94%	99.96%	99.98%	99.37%	99.86%	99.91%
8	99.16%	99.82%	99.89%	99.84%	99.91%	99.75%	99.81%	99.91%	97.30%	99.41%	99.63%
10	98.82%	99.74%	99.84%	99.76%	99.87%	99.61%	99.71%	99.86%	95.63%	99.05%	99.40%

Table 4c. Limited current efficiency for Bin 3

Use case variants →	28 [A]	29 [A]	19 [A]	13 [A]	16 [A]
Selected design variants ↓					
28	2735.35	3908.28	2985.82	1984.28	2233.97
29	2171.75	3176.32	2384.85	1539.37	1748.32
19	2730.27	3934.02	2986.76	1963.55	2217.99
13	4069.12	5705.18	4421.41	2999.71	3357.68
16	4027.11	5586.99	4364.62	2995.97	3342.33

Efficiency

Use case variants →	28	29	19	13	16
Selected design variants ↓					
28	99.16%	99.64%	99.06%	96.64%	97.48%
29	98.05%	99.16%	97.83%	92.34%	94.25%
19	98.96%	99.55%	98.86%	96.00%	97.00%
13	99.66%	99.85%	99.64%	98.76%	99.07%
16	99.72%	99.88%	99.70%	98.96%	99.22%

The columns in Table 4 represent the use case specifications (from Table 2), and the rows in Table 4 represent the optimized design variants associated with each use case (from Table

3). The limited current value listed in each cell was calculated using the design parameters of the variant listed in the row, and the specifications of the use case listed in the column. The limited current value and the efficiency calculated for the optimized design are listed in red font (cells with the same number on the row and column).

The down selection was performed considering two criteria:

- The limited current value for a certain use case should be no larger than 120% of the value obtained with the optimized design (listed with red font in the same column).
- the corresponding efficiency (the corresponding cell in the Efficiency table) should not be below 98.5%.

After analysing the values in Table 4, the cells highlighted in yellow are complying with both restrictions. The strategy is to select the minimum number of design variants (minimum number of rows) that covers at least one yellow highlighted cell for each use case listed in the columns. The selected designs, listed in Table 5 (rows), are covering all the targeted use cases. For use case 20, because the optimization method did not find an optimized design, it is proposed to use design variant 21. Even if the estimated limited current value is about 80 time higher than the nominal current (84.82 A vs. 1 A), this design is the most suitable among the design variants included in the study.

Table 5. Selected design variants

Use case bin	Design variant	Nominal Current [A]	Nominal Voltage [V]	Fault Current [A]	Efficiency	Number of Turns	Airgap Length [m]	Core Cross Section [m ²]	EMR Chip Thickness [m]	EMR Chip Length [m]	EMR Chip Width [m]
Bin 1	21	4	48	84.5	99.85	24	0.0012	0.00015	0.0027	0.0084	0.001
	25	32	350	426.7	98.96	32	0.0051	0.00026	0.0043	0.0084	0.0012
	2	50	48	429.8	99.39	36	0.0172	0.00074	0.0018	0.0133	0.0017
Bin 2	5	100	48	813.5	99.44	24	0.0212	0.00094	0.0021	0.0299	0.0024
	9	100	350	953.8	99.26	20	0.0147	0.0015	0.0071	0.0324	0.0011
	6	200	48	1464.4	99.2	21	0.0315	0.0054	0.0034	0.05	0.0046
Bin 3	28	380	650	2789	98.68	14	0.0321	0.0031	0.0049	0.0356	0.0012
	29	380	1500	3226.5	98.21	19	0.0375	0.0087	0.0016	0.0058	0.0011
	13	500	300	3043.2	98.69	10	0.0393	0.0035	0.0034	0.0367	0.0012
	30	1600	1500	9731.2	98.38	3	0.0326	0.0026	0.0025	0.0223	0.0011

7. Conclusion & Next Steps

The High-Level Use Cases (HLUC) that we targeted are covering the main areas where the DC power is currently used to enable the energy transition. Each HLUC has several specification domains, corresponding to grid specifications that can perform the required tasks. The 5 HLUCs included 30 individual use cases, with various levels of nominal current and voltage, with increasing power capabilities.

Considering our proposed current limiter concept, a mathematical and simulation framework was developed and employed to determine the optimum design parameters of the current limiter for each of the 30 identified use cases. The optimum design included the magnetic field generator (core cross section, airgap size, number of coil turns), as well as the EMR chip dimensions, assuming the rectangular stack (“sandwich”) concept.

After identifying the values for the parameters in optimum design each use case, a down selection method was proposed and employed to reduce the number of design variants from 30 to 10.

Depending on the use application requirements (short circuit current level, space restrictions for the current limiter) the number of design variants can be further reduced by keeping only the devices optimized for higher currents and power levels, if lower efficiencies are accepted for that application.

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